

Supplementary Material 4: Questionnaires and Interview Schedules

- a. Ammunition study: participant questionnaire
- b. Cat management study: participant questionnaire
- c. Cat management study: Q sort procedure and post-sort interview schedule

S4a: Ammunition study: participant questionnaire

Participant ID:

Questionnaire

(I) Socio-demographic information

1. Which age group do you fall within? (please circle your answer)

18-24

25-34

35-44

45-55

55-64

65+

2. What is your occupation? _____

(II) Knowledge

Please circle your answer:

3. My knowledge about this topic **mainly** comes from:

a. Shooting and country media

b. Shooting contacts

c. Other _____ Please explain _____

[choose one answer only]

4. What level of knowledge on this topic do you have:

a. High level of knowledge

b. Moderate level of knowledge

c. Low level of knowledge

d. No knowledge

e. I don't know

(iii) Shooting habits

5. How often do you use non-toxic shot?

a. Very frequently

b. Frequently

c. Occasionally

d. Rarely

e. Very rarely

f. Never

6. What is your main quarry species? _____

7. How do you **mainly** access your shooting? Please circle your answer:

a. Through commercial days

b. Through a syndicate/club

c. Through local contacts

d. Other (please describe)? _____

S4b: Cat management study: participant questionnaire

Q Study Participant Questionnaire

Your personal details and all information you provide in this questionnaire will be stored securely, and will not be shared with anyone beyond the research team. Any responses you provide here, if used in published research, will be fully anonymised.

* Required

1. Q Sort ID *

Please ask the researcher if you have not been told your Q Sort ID.

2. First Name *

3. Surname *

4. Gender

5. Date of Birth

US format - MONTH, DAY, YEAR

Example: December 15, 2012

6. Postcode

This will only be used to identify your region and housing density in your area.

For most of these questions, you can select more than one option.

7. How many cats are associated with your household?

8. How many of your cats are female?

9. How many of your cats fall into the following age groups?

Check all that apply.

	1	2	3	4	5 or more
Less than 6 months old	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6 months - 1 year old	<input type="checkbox"/>				
1 - 5 years old	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6 - 10 years old	<input type="checkbox"/>				
11 - 15 years old	<input type="checkbox"/>				
15 - 20 years old	<input type="checkbox"/>				
More than 20 years old	<input type="checkbox"/>				

10. What breed(s) of cat do you have?

Check all that apply.

- Domestic shorthair OR domestic longhair ('moggie')
- British Shorthair
- Persian
- Bengal
- Siamese
- Ragdoll
- Maine Coon
- Burmese
- Norwegian Forest
- Other: _____

11. Where did your cats come from?

Check all that apply.

- Non-pedigree breeder
- Pedigree breeder
- Sanctuary or rescue centre
- Rehomed from elsewhere (e.g. a friend, advert)
- I own(ed) the mother
- A farm
- I adopted a stray
- Other: _____

12. Do you keep your cat(s)...

Mark only one oval.

- Indoor (contained within house)
- Indoor / outdoor contained (e.g. with fencing, catio)
- Indoor / outdoor regulated (e.g. kept in at night)
- Indoor / outdoor unregulated (e.g. cat flap)
- Outdoor (no access to house)
- I have different rules for different cats.

Skip to question 13.

Knowledge of hunting

13. **To the best of your knowledge, do one or more of your cats hunt wild animals?**

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 14.*
 No *Stop filling out this form.*

Hunting behaviour

14. **Are one or more of your cats kept for pest control purposes?**

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

15. **Roughly how often do one or more of your cats bring prey home?**

Mark only one oval.

- Daily
 Weekly
 Monthly
 Seasonally (e.g. only in spring)
 Rarely
 Never

16. **When was the last time you remember prey being brought in?**

17. **Have you ever tried to manage your cats' hunting?**

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 18.*
 No *Stop filling out this form.*

Hunting Management

18. **In what ways have you tried to manage your cats' hunting?**

(e.g. collar-mounted devices; keeping your cat in at certain times; fencing your garden; and anything else you might have tried)

19. Do you think the things you have tried are effective at reducing hunting?

S4c: Cat management study: Q sort procedure and post-sort interview schedule

Q Sort Procedure

1. Introduction

- *Check has received initial information sheet / letter of invitation*
- "This study is designed to help us understand cat owners' views on a range of issues surrounding their pets' roaming and hunting behaviour. There are 62 cards in this deck, and they all have a different statement on them. These are all real statements made by cat owners, though some of them have been edited for clarity. We are going to ask how much you agree or disagree with the statement on each card. I'll talk you through the process as we go."

2. Consent form (paper)

3. Instructions

- First, go through this deck of cards and separate them into three piles: ones you definitely agree with, ones you definitely disagree with, and ones you're not sure about. You can change your mind later.
- You might think that some of the statements are facts that are either true or not. When you see statements like this, place them in the 'agree' pile if you believe them to be true, and the 'disagree' file if you believe them to be false.

Allow time for first sort – lay out distribution cards

- I've laid out these cards along the top of the table to show you how we would like you to sort the statements.
- Each of these cards has a number on it – that tells you how many statements you should put below that card.
- Those you agree with will be on this end, and those you disagree with this end. The ones you are not sure about, or don't care about, will go in the middle. There is lots of room in the middle for the cards you feel less strongly about.
- When you've finished, your sort will look something like this (*show photo*).
- Most people find it easiest to start with either the 'agree' or 'disagree' pile and fill in one end; then fill in the other end; then fill in the middle.
- If you take one pile now, to get started, spread them all out in front of you and start moving the ones you feel strongly about this way – this will help you compare the cards against one another.
- You might have to make some decisions about which you feel more strongly about, but don't panic about it being perfect – the difference between a card being in one column or another is quite small.

Allow time for the arranging of cards.

- Have a look at the whole spread together, and see if you want to move any around.

4. Post-Sort Interview

Switch on audio recorder

- Do you feel the spread accurately represents your views?
- Is there anything you strongly believe or feel that isn't represented here?
- Tell me about the two statements you disagreed most strongly with.

- Tell me about the two statements you agreed most strongly with.
- Were there issues raised by these statements that you hadn't thought about before? (Which?)
- Can you summarise your views on cat roaming and hunting behaviour in a couple of sentences?

Switch off recorder

- Is there anything you want to ask me about the study?

5. Participant Questionnaire (iPad)

6. (If away from home - participant leaves)

7. Data recording

- *Turn over all cards to show numbers*
- *Take photo of sort with sort number visible*

8. (If at participant's home – researcher leaves)

- *Input data directly onto spreadsheet – invert if required!*
- *Save spreadsheet*